

Stability Constants of Methylmercuric Carboxylates.

A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar-4

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Complex formation between CH_3Hg^+ ion and carboxylate ligands has been studied potentiometrically. The thermodynamic dissociation constants of methylmercuric acetate, *n*-butyrate, phenylacetate, and lactate are found to be $5.64(\pm 0.60) \times 10^{-4}$ (35°), $8.2(\pm 1.8) \times 10^{-4}$ (25°), $2.4(\pm 0.5) \times 10^{-4}$ (25°), and $6.7(\pm 1.1) \times 10^{-4}$ (29°) respectively.

THE ionisation constants of several alkyl and aryl mercuric hydroxides (RHgOH) and halides (RHgX $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-$) have recently been determined¹⁻³. Interaction of CH_3Hg^+ ion with ligands possessing O, N, S, and P donor functions has also been investigated⁴. Anionic complexes of the type $\text{RHgX}_n^{(n-1)-}$ ($n < 3$) have been shown to exist in solution at relatively high concentration of the ligands⁵. However, systematic study of the dissociation equilibria of the organomercuric carboxylates has not yet been attempted. In this paper the results of our study of the equilibria involving CH_3Hg^+ ion and ligands like acetate, *n*-butyrate, lactate, and phenylacetate have been reported.

Experimental

Methylmercuric iodide was prepared by the method of Maynard⁶ and purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol. Methylmercuric acetate was prepared by the interaction of methylmercuric iodide with silver acetate in methanol and purified by repeated crystallization from methanol. The organomercurials were stored over fused calcium chloride in a black painted desiccator in order to prevent photo-decomposition.

Standard solution of methylmercuric acetate was prepared by weight. The concentration of CH_3Hg^+ ion was also checked by estimating Hg as HgS after decomposing methylmercuric acetate with (3:1) HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 mixture⁵. The concentration of CH_3Hg^+ ion in the stock solution, calculated from the weight of methylmercuric acetate, was found to be 0.8% higher than the same calculated from the weight of HgS .

Methylmercuric perchlorate⁷ was prepared from methylmercuric iodide and silver perchlorate. Stock solution of methylmercuric perchlorate was stored in the refrigerator in a measuring flask painted black. The concentration of CH_3Hg^+ ion in the stock solution of $\text{CH}_3\text{HgClO}_4$ was determined by estimating Hg as HgS . Fresh solution of $\text{CH}_3\text{HgClO}_4$ was prepared and estimated from time to time.

The organic acids (B.D.H., A.R. or E.Merck extra pure) and perchloric acid (E.Merck, G.R.) were

standardised against sodium hydroxide (B.D.H., A.R.). Potassium hydrogenphthalate (E.Merck, G.R.) was used to standardise sodium hydroxide. All solutions were prepared in freshly prepared conductivity water.

pH measurement :

Solutions of requisite composition were prepared in 100 ml measuring flasks. pH of such solutions was measured with a battery operated Marconi pH meter model TF511d. The glass electrode was standardised against tetroxalate (pH = 1.86), phthalate (pH = 4.01), and phosphate (pH = 6.86) buffers.

Results and Discussion

It is known that the first ligand attached to an alkylmercuric cation (RHg^+) is strongly bound to the mercury atom. $\text{RHgX}_n^{(n-1)-}$ ($n > 1$) species are formed when the concentration of the ligand, X^- , is maintained sufficiently high relative to that of RHg^+ ion. In the present work the concentrations of the carboxylate ligands were comparable with that of CH_3Hg^+ ion. As such the equilibria existing in solutions containing CH_3Hg^+ ion and the carboxylate ligands may be represented as

where α , β stand for the degree of association and hydrolysis of CH_3Hg^+ ion respectively and γ is the degree of dissociation of the carboxylic acid, HA. $\text{CH}_3\text{HgClO}_4$ has been taken to be completely dissociated⁷ under the experimental conditions. Let C_1 , C_2 , C_3 and C_4 be the total initial concentration of CH_3Hg^+ , HClO_4 , NaA and HA respectively.

TABLE I—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF CH₃HgA SPECIES

A⁻ = CH₃COO⁻

Temp. = 35°

K_b⁴ = 5.23 × 10⁻¹⁰, K_{HA}⁹ = 1.73 × 10⁻⁵, K_w⁹ = 2.06 × 10⁻¹⁴.

10 ² [CH ₃ HgA], (M)	10 ² [HA], (M)	pH	α	β	γ	10 ³ μ, (M)	K _d , (M)
1.00	11.28	3.12	0.799	0.0464	0.0063	2.7	5.81 × 10 ⁻⁴
2.00	25.68	2.96	0.835	0.0322	0.0042	4.4	7.18
3.00	33.85	2.82	0.913	0.0236	0.0046	3.9	3.15
4.00	45.14	2.80	0.907	0.0224	0.0036	5.0	4.23
2.50	33.21	2.90	0.855	0.0281	0.0038	4.9	6.85
3.50	44.50	2.84	0.877	0.0244	0.0033	5.8	6.63

$K_{d(av)} = 5.64(\pm 0.60) \times 10^{-4}$

A⁻ = CH₃CH₂COO⁻

Temp. = 25°

K_b⁴ = 3.28 × 10⁻¹⁰, K_{HA}⁹ = 1.51 × 10⁻⁵, K_w⁹ = 1.01 × 10⁻¹⁴.

10 ³ [CH ₃ H ₂ ClO ₄], (M)	10 ³ [HClO ₄], (M)	10 ³ [NaA], (M)	10 ³ [HA], (M)	pH	α	β	10 ³ μ, (M)	K _d , (M)
2.03	0.423	5.00	20.0	4.03	0.785	0.232	5.4	6.42 × 10 ⁻⁴
1.42	0.296	4.80	20.0	4.08	0.769	0.262	5.1	7.90
2.03	0.423	5.40	24.0	4.02	0.774	0.227	5.8	7.99
1.62	0.338	5.00	24.0	4.02	0.720	0.228	5.4	10.70

$K_{d(av)} = 8.2(\pm 1.8) \times 10^{-4}$

A⁻ = C₆H₅CH₂COO⁻

Temp. = 25°

K_b⁴ = 3.28 × 10⁻¹⁰, K_{HA}¹⁰ = 4.89 × 10⁻⁵, K_w⁹ = 1.01 × 10⁻¹⁴.

10 ³ [CH ₃ H ₂ ClO ₄], (M)	10 ³ [HClO ₄], (M)	10 ³ [NaA], (M)	10 ³ [HA], (M)	pH	α	β	10 ³ μ, (M)	K _d , (M)
1.00	1g727	2.62	0.00	4.00	0.523	0.223	3.1	2.28 × 10 ⁻⁴
1.20	1.769	3.14	0.00	4.03	0.645	0.235	3.5	2.18
2.44	0.507	3.66	3.00	4.01	0.768	0.186	4.2	2.71
2.44	0.507	3.14	3.20	3.92	0.687	0.169	3.9	3.12
1.83	0.380	2.62	2.40	4.01	0.750	0.228	3.0	1.96
2.03	0.423	3.14	3.20	3.97	0.732	0.211	3.7	3.09
2.84	0.592	3.14	2.40	3.88	0.720	0.178	3.9	1.37

$K_{d(av)} = 2.4(\pm 0.5) \times 10^{-4}$

A⁻ = CH₃CH(OH)COO⁻

Temp. = 29°

K_b⁴ = 4.16 × 10⁻¹⁰, K_{AH}⁹ = 1.35 × 10⁻⁵, K_w⁹ = 1.37 × 10⁻¹⁴.

10 ³ [CH ₃ H ₂ ClO ₄], (M)	10 ³ [HClO ₄], (M)	10 ³ [NaA], (M)	10 ³ [HA], (M)	pH	α	β	10 ³ μ, (M)	K, (M)
1.00	1.29	3.14	0.00	4.00	0.545	0.235	3.6	7.24 × 10 ⁻⁴
1.20	1.33	3.14	0.00	3.92	0.472	0.203	3.8	7.61
1.40	1.38	3.66	0.00	3.97	0.629	0.222	4.2	5.56
1.60	1.42	3.14	0.00	3.86	0.490	0.182	3.9	6.90
2.00	1.50	3.92	0.00	3.90	0.620	0.188	4.7	5.03
1.20	1.55	3.14	0.00	3.82	0.471	0.203	3.8	7.93

$K_{d(av)} = 6.7(\pm 1.1) \times 10^{-4}$

The equilibrium concentrations of different species are given by

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{CH}_3\text{Hg}^+] &= (1-\beta)(1-\alpha)C_1, \\ [\text{CH}_3\text{HgA}] &= \alpha C_1, \\ [\text{CH}_3\text{HgOH}] &= \beta(1-\alpha)C_1, \\ [\text{HA}] &= (1-\gamma)(C_2+C_4), \\ [\text{H}^+] &= \beta(1-\alpha)C_1 + \gamma(C_2+C_4), \text{ and} \\ [\text{A}^-] &= (C_3+C_4) - \alpha C_1 - (1-\gamma)(C_2+C_4). \end{aligned}$$

It can easily be shown that

$$\beta = \frac{1}{1 + (K_b/K_w) \times (\alpha_{\text{H}^+})/f_+} \quad \dots (1)$$

where K_b , K_w stand for the basic dissociation constant, of CH_3HgOH and ionic product of water respectively (α_{H^+} is the activity of hydrogen ion and f_+ is the activity coefficient of CH_3Hg^+ ion. The activity coefficient of CH_3HgOH is taken to be unity. The dissociation constant (K_{HA}) of the carboxylic acid may be expressed as

$$K_{\text{HA}} = \frac{\{C_3 + C_4 - \alpha C_1 - (1-\gamma)(C_2 + C_4)\}(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})f_-}{(1-\gamma)(C_2 + C_4)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where f_- = the activity coefficient of A^- and the activity coefficient of HA is taken to be unity. Utilising the relationship for $[\text{H}^+]$, assuming $f_+ = f_{\text{H}^+}$ and rearranging eq. (2), α and γ may be expressed as

$$\alpha = 1 + \frac{\gamma(C_2 + C_4)}{\beta C_1} - \frac{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})}{\beta C_1 f_+} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\gamma = P/Q \quad \dots (4)$$

where

$$P = C_3 - C_1 - C_2 + \frac{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})}{\beta f_+} - \frac{K_{\text{HA}}(C_2 + C_4)}{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})f_-} \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$Q = \left\{ \frac{1}{\beta} - \left(1 + \frac{K_{\text{HA}}}{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})f_-} \right) \right\} (C_2 + C_4) \quad \dots (6)$$

The expression for ionic strength is given as

$$\mu = C_3 + (1-\alpha)C_1 + \gamma(C_2 + C_4) \quad \dots (7)$$

As a first approximation μ was taken to be C_3 . The activity coefficient was calculated from Davies equation⁸. From the known values of K_b , K_w , and (α_{H^+}) , β was calculated from eq. (1). The values of γ calculated from eq. (4) turned out to be negative for *n*-butyrate, lactate and phenylacetate systems. As such γ was taken to be zero and then α was calculated from eq. (3). The ionic strength was then refined (eq. 7). With $\gamma = 0$, the calculation of α , β was repeated till the ionic strength turned out to be virtually constant. The thermodynamic dissociation constants (K_d) of CH_3HgA species were

calculated from the refined values of α , β and f_+ assuming $f_+ = f_-$, $f_{(\text{CH}_3\text{Hg}_i\text{A})} = 1$ and $\gamma = 0$.

It may be noted that the study of the dissociation equilibrium of methylmercuric acetate involved measurement of *pH* of solutions containing methylmercuric acetate and acetic acid. The expressions for α , γ and μ for this system take the form :

$$\alpha = 1 + \frac{\gamma C_4}{\beta C_1} - \frac{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})}{\beta C_1 f_+} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\gamma = P'/Q' \quad \dots (9)$$

where

$$P' = \frac{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})}{\beta f_+} - \frac{K_{\text{HA}}C_4}{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})f_-} \quad \dots (10)$$

$$Q' = \frac{C_4}{\beta} - \left(1 + \frac{K_{\text{HA}}}{(\alpha_{\text{H}^+})f_+} \right) C_4 \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\mu = (1-\alpha)C_1 + \gamma C_4. \quad \dots (12)$$

The values of α , β , γ , and μ for this system were calculated by an iterative procedure starting with the initial approximation $\mu = 0$. The results of the *pH* measurements and the thermodynamic dissociation constants of CH_3HgA species have been collected in Table 1.

The conductivity studies of Maynard¹¹ indicated that methylmercuric acetate is a weak electrolyte. Simpson² has given a value of 2.15×10^{-4} for the dissociation constant of methylmercuric acetate at 25° from polarographic measurement. The thermodynamic dissociation constant of $\text{CH}_3\text{HgOOCCH}_3$ obtained in the present work ($5.64(\pm 0.60) \times 10^{-4}$) compares well with Simpson's data. The dissociation constants of acetate, lactate, *n*-butyrate, and phenylacetate complexes of methylmercuric ion are also comparable to each other. These results indicate that the stabilities of CH_3HgA species are little influenced by the steric effect of the carboxylate ligands and lactate ion does not act as a chelating agent towards CH_3Hg^+ .

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